

AL-FARABI ABOUT THE VIRTUOUS CITY

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Abstract. *The given article presents the formation of al-Farabi as an Arab political philosopher, Al-Farabi's contributions to Islamic philosophy. An Islamic philosophical utopia is also considered, which al-Farabi (872-951) began with his project of Virtuous City, guaranteeing all people a happy life in comprehension of Truth and in harmony with the Cosmos.*

Keywords: *second teacher, metaphysics, Virtuous city.*

The research methods of the article are a systematic historical and philosophical approach, as well as a comparative historical method.

The analysis and results of the article consist in an analysis of the approach to the problem of the "ideal city" using the example of the peripatetic trend in Islamic culture of the medieval period.

Introduction. It is important to suggest that Al-Farabi is considered the father of Arabic political philosophy. Al-Farabi (Latin: Alfarabius), or "the Second Teacher" (al-mu'allim as sani), was born in Farab, modern place of Kazakhstan, in around 870 year. As a young man, he went to Baghdad to study logic and philosophy with Matta ibn Yunus, and then to Harran, where he became a student of Yuhann ibn Haylan. Possessing a keen mind from an early age and a gift for quickly mastering almost any subject he studied, Al-Farabi soon became a famous philosopher and scholar. He returned to Baghdad, where a group of students gathered around him, including the famous Christian philosopher Yahya ibn Adi. However, Al-Farabi's stay in the capital of Abbasid Caliphate came to an end in 941, when he left Baghdad for Aleppo to the court of Sayf al-Dawla al-Hamadani, where Al-Farabi remained until his death in 950. Al-Farabi is considered as a great commentator and follower of Aristotle. He wrote commentaries on "Aristotle's Categories", "On Interpretation", "First Analytics", "Second Analytics", "Sophistic Refutations", "Rhetoric", "Poetics", "Nicomachean Ethics", "Physics", "On the Heavens", and "Meteorology", as well as "Porphyry's Isagoge", which is devoted to logic. Al-Farabi also wrote commentaries on Aristotle's Metaphysics, which also influenced Avicenna's understanding of Aristotle's metaphysics. The most valuable works are Al-Farabi's writings on logic, in which Aristotelian logic was expounded in adequate Arabic terminology, which has since become an indispensable element of Islamic scholarship in general.

Despite his loyalty to the Aristotelian proof, he tried to unite the views of Aristotle and Plato and, like almost all Islamic thinkers, believed that the teachings of these philosophers must have had their source in divine revelation and therefore should not contain contradictions. To this end, he wrote several works, the most famous of which is "Kitab al-jam bayna rayai al-hakimain Aflatun al-ilahi wa Aristu" (The Book on the Commonality of the Views of the Two Philosophers, the Divine Plato and Aristotle), in which Al-Farabi tried to reconcile the two ancient philosophers.

The most influential work in the East, which is still read and studied in madrassas at present time is the famous text of "Al-Farabi Fusus al-hikam" (Gems of Wisdom). Over the course of many centuries, this text has been repeatedly commented on it. Thus, the "Second Teacher",

famous for his commentary and popularization of the works of Aristotle, as well as for the creation of Arabic logical terminology, was also a political philosopher, a follower of Plato, a scientist, a gifted mathematician and musician.

It is important to suggest that Al-Farabi in his treatise “A Word on the Classification of Sciences” singles out civil science, indicating that it “studies the types of actions and behavior conditioned by the will; properties, morals, innate qualities and characters from which these actions and behavior originate; the goals for which they are committed; why they should be in a person, how they should be located in him in the form in which they should exist in him; the way of preserving them in him. It also explains which goals are real happiness, and which are imaginary happiness.”

According to his teaching, a great society is the totality of societies of all people inhabiting the earth, an average society is a society represented by one nation and a small society is a society represented by the inhabitants of a city occupying a certain part of the area inhabited by a particular nation. Incomplete societies are made up of the inhabitants of a village and the totality of the inhabitants of a block, then the totality of those who live on a single street, then the totality of those who live in a single house. The latter constitute a society of the lowest order.

Definitely, the block and the village together belong to the city, but only the village belongs to the city in the sense that it serves the city, while the block belongs to the city, forming a part of it. The street is part of the block, the house is part of the street, the city is part of the locality, the people are part of the totality of the inhabitants of the earth.

Certainly, the greatest good and the highest perfection can be achieved first by a city, but not by a society at a lower level of perfection. A city in which the union of people aims at mutual assistance in matters by which true happiness is found is a virtuous city, and a society in which people help each other in order to achieve happiness is a virtuous society. A nation in which all the cities help each other in order to achieve happiness is a virtuous nation. In the same way, the whole earth will become virtuous if the nations help each other to achieve happiness.

Besides that, a virtuous city is like a perfect, healthy body, all the organs of which help each other in order to preserve the life of a living being and make it as complete as possible. In the same way, the organs of the body differ from each other, surpassing each other in their nature and their abilities in relation to the main organ, the heart.

The first stage at which a person becomes a person is when a natural form appears, capable and ready to become reason in action. While overflowing, overflows from Allah, the blessed and the Highest, to the active mind, overflows through the medium of the acquired mind, and then to its faculty of imagination. This man becomes a sage, a philosopher, the possessor of a perfect mind, a prophet, a soothsayer of the future and an interpreter of current private events and all this thanks to the existence in which he cognizes the divine.

Additionally, such person possesses the highest degree of human perfection and is at the height of happiness. His soul is perfect. This person is the one, who knows every action by which happiness can be achieved. This is the first condition that the head must satisfy. Further, he must have the ability to convey well, figuratively, in words everything he knows; he must be able to best direct people to happiness and to those actions by which it is achieved; he must have sufficient physical strength to carry out particular actions. The head, a man who is not subject to any of the people, he is the imam, this is the first head of the virtuous city, this is the head of the virtuous

people and the head of the entire inhabited part of the earth. Only he, who combines in himself twelve innate natural qualities can become such a person. A person must have:

- firstly, absolutely perfect organs, the powers of which are so well adapted to the performance of those actions that they must perform that if this person undertakes any action with the help of any organ, he performs it with ease;

- to be able by nature to perfectly understand and imagine everything that is said to him, comprehending what is said to him in accordance with what the speaker means and with how things are in themselves;

- to retain well in memory everything that he understands, sees, hears and perceives, forgetting almost nothing of all this;

- to have a penetrating and insightful mind, so that, having noticed the slightest sign of any thing, he could quickly grasp what this sign indicates; to have an expressive style and be able to express with complete clarity everything that he conceives;

- to have a love for learning and knowledge, achieving this easily, without experiencing either fatigue from learning or torment from the associated work;

- to be abstinent in food, in drinking and in intercourse, by nature to avoid gambling and to feel disgust for the pleasures that arise from it;

- to love the truth and its champions, to hate lies and those who resort to it;

- to have a proud soul and to value honor: his soul by nature should be above all low deeds and by nature strive for sublime deeds;

- to despise dirhams, dinars and other attributes of worldly life;

- to love justice by nature and its champions, to hate injustice and tyranny and those from whom they come;

- to be fair to his own people and to strangers, to encourage justice and to compensate the victims of injustice, giving to all what he considers good and beautiful;

- to be fair, but not stubborn, not to show willfulness and not to persist in the face of justice, but to be completely adamant in the face of all injustice and baseness;

- to show determination in doing what he considers necessary and at the same time to be bold, courageous, not to know fear and cowardice.

It is not a secret that the combination of all this in one person is a difficult thing and that is why people gifted with such a nature are very rare and form only a minority. So, if such a person is found in a virtuous city and the first six conditions mentioned above, or five of them are realized in him, when he grows up, then, having no equal in the capacity of imagination, he will become the head of this city. But, if it happens that such a person is not found at one time or another, then the laws and rules established by the head of the city and his successors, if such have successively become the head of the city are maintained.

Certainly, a virtuous city is opposed to an ignorant city, an immoral city, a city of deceit and a city that has gone astray. Equally opposed to it are the individuals who represent these cities.

It is known to everyone that an ignorant city is one, whose inhabitants have never known happiness and it has never occurred to them to strive for it. They have never known it and have never believed in it. As for the goods, they know only those of them which only apparently pass for goods in the opinions of people, and which only in the opinions of people appear as the goals of life - such are bodily health, wealth, pleasures, freedom to indulge in one's passions, honors and

greatness. Each of these goods is already happiness in the eyes of all the inhabitants of the ignorant city.

The greatest and most complete happiness consists in the union of all these blessings. And these blessings are opposed to misfortunes, such as illnesses of the body, poverty, lack of pleasures, impossibility of following one's passions, and lack of honors.

An ignorant city is divided into several cities. The rulers of these cities are the opposite of the rulers of virtuous cities; the government of some is completely opposite to the government of others; the same applies to all their other inhabitants.

Conclusions. By summarizing it should be suggested that the rulers of virtuous cities, following one another in time, representing as it was a single soul and as it was a single eternal sovereign. Likewise, if it happens that at one and the same time, there are several virtuous sovereigns in one or more cities, then all of them together will represent, as it was a single sovereign, and their souls as it was a single soul. The case is the same with the inhabitants of a city of all other degrees: living at different times and following one another, they all form, as it was a single eternal soul. Likewise, if at the same time there are several people of the same degree in one or many cities, then their souls will constitute, as it was a single soul, regardless of whether these people, according to their degrees, relating to those who are in charge or to those who serve.

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